

Appreciating the recent advancement made in GIS by the development of Spatial Big Data.

However, you look at it, GIS is an unseen world, a space that represents graphs, polygon points and lines. Today, Big Data technology can presently process huge sets of data in the shortest curve, it has since become the new frontier for geospatial analysis. Big Data is represented by three Vs namely, volume, velocity and variety. Analyzing this data can be very challenging thanks to the improvement in the processing power of hardware and advancement of software developments which has increased the chances for using Big Data technology to process geospatial data.

Geospatial application requires selection, collection, sorting and end-usage of data. We live in a time where geo-data and remote sensing has been embraced by massive data availability. Today, analysis and mapping has increasingly been complicated with the emergence of disruptive services like embedded sensors, social media, mobile and cloud computing. Many thanks to platforms like Esri who have kept with the recent developments to provide Esri ArcGIS extensions which help to provide more insights of patterns, trends and relationship in the spatial space.

Unstructured and Structured data in spatial analysis

If you consider the prominent spatial data convention, you will notice that Graphs, Vectors and Raster has become the common reference. SBD of raster types involves satellite imagery, coordinated drone imaging system and climate simulation. You can see the SBD in vector types which has been experienced in data from Taxi like Uber, twitter data for geo-locations, gps and so on. SBD in graph data can be seen in electric grid data, road network data, supply chain network data.

Processing Spatial Big Data

Data has fast become the greatest processing asset in this age. With so much data available in all forms of sustainable livelihood. Data has different characteristics which includes, value, variance, volume, velocity and virtualization. Before now these data ingredients could not be fully analyze representing a significant loss of information. With the advent of Google map-reduce framework which is a programming model used for processing large data-sets, most of the real world task can be converted into Map-Reduce function type. To fully appreciate the Map-Reduce framework in Geo-Spatial big data issues, it would be appropriate to convert it into two functions namely- Mapping and Reducing.

Hadoop-GIS

Hadoop-GIS is a high performance, scalable spatial data-ware housing system which runs on Hadoop. It agrees with partitioning of spatial spaces, customizing spatial query using techniques like RESQUE. A unique aspect of the Hadoop-GIS is that it uses global partition indexing to realize its query result which bring a lot of efficiency. Ultimately, it supports spatial queries such as containment, join, point and other complex queries like nearest neighbor queries and spatial cross matching. Designed with the intent of bringing cost-effective, highly scalable and efficient spatial querying system, Hadoop-GIS remains a formidable processing technique for querying spatial dataset.

Spatial Hadoop

This an extension of Hadoop which increasingly supports native spatial data. Spatial Hadoop takes on a more traditional approach of indexing spatial structures, Grid, R+-tree and R-tree to create a two-level spatial index. With in-built Hadoop base code, Spatial Hadoop can be informed of spatial constructs and spatial data required to increase its power and efficiency. Generally Spatial Hadoop has for parts namely, language, storage, operational layer and Mapreduce.

The above architecture explains how developers can be able to relate at the spatial operations level and can perform a large set of query such as RangeQuery, SpatialJoin and so on. While System Admin can explore the configuration files and parameters and the casual users can do simple spatial query and observe the result through the visualization tool.

References.

Bedard Y., 2014, *Beyond GIS: Spatial On-Line Analytical Processing and Big Data*, Univ. of Maine [Online]

Chen Y, Suel T., Markowetz A., 2006, *Efficient Query Processing in Geographic Web Search Engines* [Onlin